

RECEPTION OF APOSIOPESIS IN MEDIA POLITICAL DISCOURSE

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Annotation: *The use of various speech strategies and tactics can incline the listener to the point of view desired by the speaker. The interest of linguists is aimed at discovering and describing all the means of such a communicative situation, in which a formally unexpressed denotation is transmitted to the speakers and is realized by the listeners. Aposiopesis is associated both with the replacement of some word forms by others, and with the formal non-representation of language units as a result of their omission.*

Key words: *aposiopesis, communication, stylistic device, emotional*

Aposiopesis is an important element of human communication. It is resorted to when the speaker does not want to go beyond etiquette or social norms, the word or expression is recognized as personally important and therefore difficult to verbalize or silence acts as a hint. Aposiopesis is understood in different ways in modern linguistics. Some researchers consider by aposiopesis the reticence of phrases, words, reflecting the high emotionality of speech. Other scientists believe that when silent, the speaker deliberately breaks off the statement and allows the addressee to guess what was left unsaid, and with aposiopesis, the speaker cannot continue the speech due to the combination of feelings (O.V. Puzanova, D.E. Rozental, E.V. Dzhandzhakova, N.P. Kabanova, M.A. Shelyakin). A.I.

Halperin considers aposiopesis or silence as one of the characteristic features of live colloquial speech, used as a stylistic device. In speech, silence is usually the result of a strong influx of feelings that prevents you from finishing the speech, or sometimes - unwillingness to continue the thought. In live speech, aposiopesis or silence is often accompanied by gestures and facial expressions. In addition, intonation also largely reveals the content of that part of the statement that remains unspoken. However, silence can act as a stylistic device that greatly increases the emotional intensity of the statement. According to I.V. Arnold (1), in the style of the text one should distinguish not only silence, but also aposiopesis close to it. Both of these means consist in an emotional interruption of the utterance, but with silence, the speaker deliberately leaves the listener to guess what was left unsaid, and with aposiopesis, he really or feignedly cannot continue the speech from excitement or indecision:

Example:

-Now look here, Anson... (The Rich Boy)

-It was more than the question of... of... (The Bridal Party)

I.V. Arnold (1) considers silence as a stylistic device, when the speaker deliberately leaves the listener to guess what was left unsaid. A stylistic device can only be a deviation

from the norm motivated by the stylistic task and organization of the context. The use of silence by the speaker correlates in a peculiar way with the basic principles and postulates of the success of the communication process, while the use of silence in the mass media political discourse can demonstrate its conditionality by communication norms, cultural and ethnic traditions of a particular society. Theoretical analysis of linguistic literature shows that the indicator of silence at the formal-grammatical level is the break of the speech chain by the speaker, when part of the message does not receive verbal expression. However, the meaning of the statement planned by the sender of the message, despite its formal incompleteness, is fully actualized in a particular discourse. The final component of such an incomplete statement is usually an ellipsis or a dash. At the prosodic level, the fact of silence is recorded due to the intonational incompleteness of the actualized statement (2).

Aposiopesis or silence makes it possible to hide everything that the communicant does not want to tell his interlocutors, which, of course, determines his main role. Silence creates significant pauses, bypasses some important points, jumping to a new thought. O.V. Puzanova states that in order to direct the recipient's thoughts in the direction necessary for the speaker, the aposiopesis technique is especially effective, since this is an effective method of persuasive suggestion, which consists in the fact that the communicant does not finish everything, the communicant does not tell everything to the end, does not verbalize in detail obvious thoughts, final conclusions, but only reports weighty factual data that the recipient independently, through his own reflections and accompanying intellectual and emotional associations, come to the final conclusions predicted by the communicant. At the same time, it should be borne in mind that aposiopesis is realized in a situation where the speaker deliberately breaks the speech chain, when part of the message does not receive verbal expression and is characterized by the speaker's desire to influence the recipient as much as possible.

On the one hand, the speaker uses silence to attract and focus the attention of the interlocutor on his thought. On the other hand, by aposiopesis, the speaker stimulates the mental activity of the addressee, encourages him to search, directs the course of his thoughts. According to O.V. Puzanova, aposiopesis provides for the truth of the speaker's statement. The use of aposiopesis reception as a communicative act can convey true or false information. Aposiopesis or silence is true if, in accordance with the intention of the speaker, events, phenomena, facts of objective reality are not subject to distortion and are easily decoded by the recipient in a specific communicative situation. Aposiopesis or silence is false when the speaker uses this technique to hide the truth and misinform the recipient. O.V. Puzanova also draws attention to the fact that aposiopesis conveys information implicitly and is a hint that can be interpreted by the recipient in different ways, while silence in the appropriate context can act as a fairly unambiguous act of speech.

The mechanism of aposiopesis decoding by the recipient takes into account extralinguistic, paralinguistic and linguistic factors of communication. The place of using the stylistic device of aposiopesis in British publications can be found in the caption to the photo or in the subtitle to the article, but not in the main text. The technique of aposiopesis

is typical for such genres as a journalistic essay, an interview, a columnist's opinion, where the author can express his assessment of a particular event or phenomenon. For press releases or news reports, the use of this stylistic device is uncharacteristic. Silence often interacts with various means of non-verbal communication (facial expressions, gestures), which explain, supplement or refute the meaning of the communicative course of the sender of the speech.

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